

This document contains additional material to the article "Asymptotic power spectra and visibilities of damped mixed modes" by Müller et al., which has been accepted for publication in *Astronomy & Astrophysics*. It consists of two additional appendices (E and F). The definition of the parameters and a description of the methods can be found in the main article.

Appendix E: Parameter study

Here, we show additional figures illustrating the dependence of the visibility and detectability of the mixed mode and multiplet signatures on the coupling strength q (Figs. E.1 and E.2) and on the phase shifts in the p- and g-mode cavity ϵ_p and ϵ_g (Figs. E.3 and E.4). The figures presented in this section illustrate that q , ϵ_p , and ϵ_g can influence both the visibility and detectability of the mixed mode and multiplet signatures. This can further complicate the interpretation of features in the observed PSD with unusually low multipole mode amplitudes.

Appendix F: Additional figures

In this section, we discuss the most important trends using the families of colored dots in Figs. 6 and 8. If the reader is interested in the PSD of a particular combination of parameters not shown here, we recommend that they plot it themselves. To do this, it is sufficient to calculate Eq. (44) for the relevant parameter combination and multiply the result by a Gaussian, as described in Sect. 4.2. The input parameters are given in the figure captions and axes, as well as in Table 1.

Appendix F.1: Additional figure for Sect. 5.2

Figure F.1 shows that the mixed modes are more pronounced in the PSD when the frequency of the nominal p-modes is approximately equal to that of a nominal g-mode. If this is the case for the majority of the observable pressure radial orders, the visibility is high. If this is not the case, the visibility is low. Since we are fixing all quantities that determine the relative position of the nominal p- and g- modes, with the exception of the period spacing, the ridges appear as a function of $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$. The dependence of $V_{\ell=1}^2$ on $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$ disappears for $|R_g| \rightarrow 0$ or 1.

Appendix F.2: Additional figures for Sect. 5.3

We first consider the cyan dots in the first row of Fig. 8 to investigate why a smaller value of $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$ seems to favor the presence of both mixed mode and multiplet signatures. Their power spectrum is shown in Fig. F.2. In all figures shown in this section, we focus on the triplets (i.e., $i = 45^\circ$). In the upper panel of Fig. F.2, we see that the multiplet signature is not detectable for most pressure-dominated modes, because it is imprinted in the contribution of the g-mode cavity to the total wave. When testing different values of $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$, we find that the multiplet signature of the gravity-dominated modes is only visible if $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$ is small. This can be understood as follows. The most important consequence of a smaller value of $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$ is the larger number of mixed modes in the observable frequency range, which we assume to range from ν_{left} to ν_{right} . Therefore, the gravity-dominated mixed modes are located at frequencies that are much closer to those of their corresponding nominal g-modes. The smaller difference between the frequencies of the mixed modes and the nominal g-modes favors the detectability of the multiplet signature, since the mixed modes can retain more of their g-mode character. In

the lower panel of Fig. F.2, we see that at smaller values of $|R_g|$, only the most pressure-dominated mixed modes are recognizable. Since there are more pressure-dominated modes at smaller $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$ due to the larger number of mixed modes, more than one mixed mode per pressure radial order is recognizable at smaller $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$ and the mixed mode signature is detectable.

Next, we consider the green dots in the second row of Fig. 8 to investigate the two abrupt changes between the two dots. Their power spectra are shown in Fig. F.3. The first change is that the multiplet signature can no longer be distinguished from the mixed mode signature for the lower value of $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$. This can be clearly seen in Fig. F.3, as the frequencies of the nominal g-modes shifted by $\delta\nu$ ($m = \pm 1$) almost overlap with those of the unshifted g-modes ($m = 0$) for the lower value of $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$. The second change is that the mixed mode signature suddenly becomes recognizable again for the lower value of $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$. This is also because frequencies of the modes shifted by $\delta\nu$ now almost coincide with those of the unshifted g-modes, thus reducing the number of observable peaks. In other words, the frequencies of the mixed mode multiplets align with those of other multiplets, thus simplifying the observed oscillation pattern and making the mixed modes easier to detect. For the higher value of $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$, there are so many pressure-dominated mixed modes due to the triplets that the mixed mode signature is blurred. For the lower value, there are fewer peaks with greater height in the PSD, thus making them more resistant to clumping.

In Fig. F.4, we examine the PSD corresponding to the magenta dots in the bottom row of Fig. 8. In particular, we want to answer the question of why the detectability of the multiplet signature is less favorable when $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1}$ is close to 230 s or 315 s. Following a similar logic to that in Fig. F.3, Fig. F.4 shows that mode multiplets are easier to detect when their frequencies are close to those of other modes, as this reduces the apparent number of peaks in the PSD. When the frequencies of the peaks are slightly offset, as is the case for $\Delta\Pi_{\ell=1} = 230$ s and 315 s, the peaks are broader and less pronounced, thus making them less recognizable. This conceals the multiplet signature.

Fig. E.1. Same as Fig. 6, now the columns correspond to different values in the coupling strength. The middle column is identical to the one in Fig. 6.

Fig. E.2. Same as Fig. 8, now the columns correspond to different values in the coupling strength. The middle column is identical to the one in Fig. 8.

Fig. E.3. Same as Figs. 6 and 8, now as a function of the phase shift in the p-mode cavity instead of the period spacing. The first two rows correspond to the set of stellar parameters A, and the last two rows correspond to set C.

Fig. E.4. Same as Fig. E.3, now as a function of the phase shift in the g-mode cavity.

Fig. F.1. Relative power spectrum of the dipole modes as a function of frequency for the set of stellar parameters A for different values of the period spacing and $|R_p| = 0.95$ and $|R_g| = 0.5$. The corresponding visibilities are shown on the left. Gray vertical lines indicate the location of the nominal p-modes. Colored dots indicate the location of the nominal g-modes (their value on the vertical axis has no meaning). The dotted lines connect g-modes of the same radial order. The parameters corresponding to the three power spectra shown here are highlighted as cyan dots in Fig. 6.

Fig. F.2. Relative power spectrum of the dipole modes as a function of frequency for the set of stellar parameters A and two values of the period spacing. The other parameters are $\delta\nu = 0.1 \mu\text{Hz}$, $|R_p| = 0.95$, and $i = 45^\circ$. The *upper panel* corresponds to $|R_g| = 0.98$ and the *lower panel* to $|R_g| = 0.4$. Gray vertical lines indicate the location of the nominal p-modes. Colored dots indicate the location of the nominal g-modes (their value on the vertical axis has no meaning). Triangles indicate the location of the g-modes with $m = \pm 1$. In the upper panel, green circles mark resolved modes that are part of a multiplet (i.e., they do not mark resolved modes that are not part of a multiplet). In the lower panel, there are no multiplets and the colored circles mark all resolved mixed modes. The parameters corresponding to the two power spectra shown here are highlighted as cyan dots in Fig. 8.

Fig. F.3. Relative power spectrum of the dipole modes as a function of frequency for the set of stellar parameters B for two values of the period spacing. The other parameters are $\delta\nu = 0.1 \mu\text{Hz}$, $|R_p| = 0.95$, $|R_g| = 0.5$, and $i = 45^\circ$. The displayed frequency range covers the position of the nominal p-mode at the far left of the PSD. The gray vertical line indicates the location of the nominal p-mode. Colored dots indicate the location of the nominal g-modes (their value on the vertical axis has no meaning). Triangles indicate the location of the g-modes with $m = \pm 1$. Colored circles mark the resolved mixed modes. The parameters corresponding to the two power spectra shown here are highlighted as green dots in Fig. 8.

Fig. F.4. Relative power spectrum of the dipole modes as a function of frequency for the set of stellar parameters C for two values of the period spacing. The other parameters are $\delta\nu = 0.1 \mu\text{Hz}$, $|R_p| = 0.9$, $|R_g| = 0.55$, and $i = 45^\circ$. The displayed frequency range encompasses the region around a single nominal p-mode. The gray vertical line indicates the location of the nominal p-mode. Colored dots indicate the location of the nominal g-modes (their value on the vertical axis has no meaning). Triangles indicate the location of the g-modes with $m = \pm 1$. Colored circles mark the resolved mixed modes. The parameters corresponding to the two power spectra shown here are highlighted as magenta dots in Fig. 8.